

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR USING BIO-COMPATIBLE MATERIAL FOR DENTAL PROSTHESIS

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Abstract. Recent technological advancement has revolutionized the field biomedical engineering and has significantly enhanced the well being of human life. From the design and manufacturing of bio-compatible materials to the development of software for computer-aided design (CAD) modeling and simulation, biotechnology plays a crucial role in creating safe and effective dental implants. Finite element analysis has been accustomed to simulating the stresses and strains on implants helping to optimize the design and insertion process. This study aims to compare the stress profiles of Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and Titanium alloy dental implants during different stages of implant insertion depths. The study builds bone-blood interface CAD models and performs numerical simulations. The results indicate that PEEK is potentially capable of replacing Titanium alloy as a suitable material for dental implants. Additionally, the study evaluates von Mises stresses in cortical and cancellous bone and considers the impact of torque and insertion depth on stress profiles, as well as strain and deformation calculations. The results provide an insight into the usage of biocompatible materials in dental implants.

Keywords: Dental prosthesis, finite element analysis, insertion torque, biocompatible materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dental implants are prosthetic devices that are used to replace missing or damaged teeth. They are typically made of biocompatible materials like titanium or ceramic and are surgically inserted into the jawbone. The use of dental implants has emerged as increasingly popular in recent years due to their many benefits over traditional dentures or bridges. The global market for dental implants is projected to reach 6.81 billion by 2024, according to Grand View Research, Inc.[7]. The contemporary dental implant is a safe medically approved prosthesis that is placed through surgery through the mandible to restore one or more missing teeth usually made of titanium. If the screws are properly manufactured and implemented there is a high success rate of more than 95% maintenance over a five-year period [1] [2] [3].

Experts in implant dentistry strongly believe that a substantial percentage of the 5% of fails are due to imprecise insertion techniques. The use of finite element method for the placement of dental implants aims to increase the predictability and credibility of the process. Implant failure could be lessened by analyzing the stress distribution within the surrounding bone tissue during insertion. [4]. Evaluating stress profiles in the cortical and cancellous bone besides considering the outcomes of the experiment

of elements like implant design, material qualities, and surgical method are all included in the scope of FEM analysis in dental implantation. According to various studies that have examined the external geometry of implants, those with conical or tapered designs displayed greater initial mechanical anchorage and compared to those with an oblique shape, primary stability. [6]. Sugiura et al. proposed considering the height of the cortical bone crest can have a substantial impact on the maximum level of various clinical and experimental research.[7] Pure titanium or titanium alloys make up most of the dental implant systems that are now used in clinical procedures, including Straumann, Nobel Biocare, Dentsply Sirona, Zimmer Biomet, and BioHorizons. Despite their satisfactory short-term outcomes with a success rate of 90% after five years, their long term results are not entirely satisfactory, with a failure rate of up to 35% after ten years. Recent studies have demonstrated improved outcomes attributed to dental companies' contributions, with short-term failure rates reduced to 0.7-4% and over 95% of implants surviving for five years after implantation in most statistical cases [8].

According to according to Hannam et al. [9], to ensure the validity and accuracy of FEA studies, it is necessary to make comparisons with data obtained from other research or from the living subjects being modelled. Studies have shown that higher insertion torques can have an impact on the peri implant bone tissue, increasing tensile and compressive stresses [10]. Although Atieh et al. focused on stress distributions near immediately inserted implants with a wider diameter, they observed a similar pattern. FEA can be used in the medical industry to assess any structure or tissue's response to a certain stimulation and examine any biomechanical changes in the tissues. [11][12] [13].

The most well-known biomedical alloys for dental applications are Titanium (Ti) and Zirconia (Zr) [14]. Stainless steel, for bone structures and screws, 316L stainless steel was traditionally employed as an implant material but not been approved as a dental implant material. Cobalt-based alloys cast partial denture structures have been made for decades. And they are also used to framework hip prosthesis [15]. In a study, tantalum was used as a dental implant material. These implants showed a process of submerged healing that combines gradual osseointegration at the titanium interface with bone formation and differentiation inside of their permeable tantalum region. [16] [17]. In a study on rats, Webster et al. [18] investigated silicon nitride's biocompatibility and stability and discovered that it was even more bone responsive than titanium and polyether ether ketone.

PEEK, a semicrystalline linear polycyclic thermoplastic that has been proposed as a metal substitute in biomaterials and has FDA approval to be employed as an implantable material [19]. PEEK further exhibited high processability, manufacturing techniques such as injection molding and 3D printing were common [20]. PEEK slightly lessens Young's modulus in both porous and dense forms, and the addition of inorganic reinforcing phases is necessary, which has been extensively investigated. Carbon fiber is an essential reinforcing material that has been extensively employed in various fields, and carbon-fiber reinforced PEEK (CFR-PEEK) has proven to be advantageous as an implant material. Although the addition of a small amount of ZrO_2 nanoparticles was found to improve mechanical properties and reduce stress concentration at the carbon fiber interface. Hydroxyapatite, the primary component of natural bone, has great biocompatibility and is bioactive, making it the appropriate reinforcer phase in implantology. Several volume percentages of in the initial study of strengthened PEEK with HA [21].

The presiding objective referring this research work is to simulate a realistic implantation process using FEA. To achieve this, build a 3D representation of the implant. Subsequently, they construct models for the cortical and cancellous bone. The aim of present study is to focus on the torque exerted on the different steps of insertion dental implant with varying bio-compatible materials.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

FEA is a useful and effective method for analyzing complex biomechanical problems on a macro scale. This study employs two distinct types of models. The first model employs Ti-6Al-4V as the material for the dental implant, while the second model uses PEEK as the implant material. Models are kept consistent except for the material properties.

The implant, abutment, and screw are modeled as isotropic, homogeneous, and linear elastic. However, anisotropic materials comprises bone, cortical and cancellous bone as non-linear material, is incorporated in Table 1. It should be noted that the anisotropic modeling approach can lead to up to a 70% increase in stress and strain compared to isotropic models. To replicate a realistic implan-

Figure 1: Mesh Implant-Bone Model

tation process, the dental implant, cortical bone, and cancellous bone are produced as 3D models in CAD software. The 3D models of a dental implant embedded in cortical and cancellous bones along with blood interface and transient structural analysis is done. The implant features parallel 1 mm pitch threads and is cylindrical with a single threaded taper. The cortical bone, which encircles the cancellous bone, has a thickness of 1.31 mm. The intact height of the model with bone is 18 mm and the width of the bone is 14mm. The diameter of the dental implant is $\phi 3.5$ at the top and it extends to $\phi 4.5$ as threads start. The implants bottom diameter is $\phi 2.5$. Mesh creation is an essential step in finite element analysis. An intermediate size mesh is selected. The implant model, shown in figure 1, consists of brick elements 3262 and 12292 nodes. The jawbone section for the analysis, with an extent of 1.3mm for the cortical bone and 19878 brick elements and 10396 nodes, and 1460 block elements and 2454 nodes for the cancellous bone. In an entire implant placed, the total numbers of elements are 28265 and 57621 nodes for the intact implant and mandible model, respectively.

A blood-bone interface of 0.5mm is considered for contact of implant with tissue purpose. This study comprises fixed limits in the one direction displayed in and time-dependent torque imposed at the implant's top. One of the objectives on this subject research is to explore the impact of incorporating a PEEK composite material aimed at the fixture/implant on the dissipation of stress within the surrounding peri-implant bone. The study aims to evaluate the effects of the physical association that occurs amongst different interacting bodies during the exertion of torque to the peri-implant bone, through numerical analysis.

Table 1: Material properties used in the study

S/N	Material	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Modulus of Rigidity (GPa)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Density
1	Ti-6Al-4V	102			0.3	4.5
2	CFR-PEEK	18			0.39	1.32
3	Blood Interface	0.07			0.3	1.5
4	Cortical Bone		$G_x = 5$ $G_y = 7.4$ $G_z = 5.5$	$E_x = 12.7$ $E_y = 17.9$ $E_z = 22.8$	$\nu_x = 0.18$ $\nu_y = 0.21$ $\nu_z = 0.32$	1.5
5	Cancellous Bone		$G_x = 0.068$ $G_y = 0.434$ $G_z = 0.068$	$E_x = 0.21$ $E_y = 1.148$ $E_z = 1.148$	$\nu_x = 0.055$ $\nu_y = 0.31$ $\nu_z = 0.055$	1.5

3 STRESS PROFILES AT CORTICAL AND CANCELLOUS BONE

The intent of the analysis characterizes replicating the process of inserting a dental implant into the jawbone in a dynamic manner. However, due to modeling difficulties such as auto-remeshing, a simplified modeling approach is proposed to step-by-step simulate and recreate the implantation process, a few models using finite elements are designed. Each model represents a new implant placement depth, with a start from 0.5mm and increasing by 1 mm until the full 11 mm length the structure of the jawbone once the implant has been inserted.

Figure 2: Ti Stress Profile Cortical & Cancellous Bone (0.5mm-2mm)

The appropriate torque is applied during the first nine seconds of implant placement, exerted torque applied to the implant's upper portion abruptly changes from 0 to 450 N mm and stayed there for 23 seconds (8 mm depth), and then increased up to 1000 N mm during the final 14 sec of the process. The non-linear transient dynamic analysis considered the material non-linearity according to the stress strain graph.

Figure 3: CFR-PEEK Stress profile Cortical and Cancellous bone(0.5mm-1mm)

The stress magnitude varies by a maximum of 0.4 MPa during the time period between 0.5-2 sec. The results shows comparatively lowest stress in the cancellous bone since the implant does not come in immediate interaction with it. During this stage, the cancellous bone only experiences stress that is transmitted by ensuring its interaction with the cortical bone. From the time period of 2.5-5 sec, there is an immediate increase in the stress profile magnitude. The cancellous bone is in touch with the primary filament from the implant's bottom, and the cortical bone is interacting with the second thread. The stress pattern exhibits a minimal peak at 0.5 mm a consequence of the bottom thread's sole interaction with a cancellous bone at a single spot, resulting in a focus under stress. For detailed explanation of the methodology, and computational approach used in this study, refer to Ahmed Dogar, Ayesha (2023). Numerical analysis of mechanical behavior of bio-compatible materials for Dental Prosthesis-A Finite Element Analysis. Master's Thesis, National University of Science and Technology, Pakistan.

Since the exerted torque is constant across 8.5 and 26 sec, these steps are merged. As the amount of applied torque increases, the tension along the cortical bone increases. From 29.5 to 33 sec, the

stress profile exhibits a similar pattern to the previous stage from 26 to 29 sec, with a slight reduction in stress levels. The key factor causing the reduction in stress levels is the expanded surface area of contact among the implant and cancellous bone.

To promote healthy bone growth recommended a stress range in the cancellous bone of 1.72 to 2.76 MPa. A significant portion of the observed stress levels from 5.5 to 36 s lie between 2.72 and 3.76 MPa, and the stress level from 0.5 to 5 s is below 1.76 MPa. At the lower and upper thread levels, some stress peaks, though, are greater than 2.76 MPa. To reach the desired stress levels that would result in the best osseointegration, proper management of the time dependent torque is essential [11].

Figure 4: Deformation & Strain

For the time period of 0.5 to 2.5 sec, the maximal stress increases from the distance from the implant to 8 to 12 MPa. In contrast as, when the distance from the implant neck rises, the stress magnitude considerably declines to less than 2-4 MPa. During the time range between 2.5 and 5 sec the stress at the implant neck increases to an assortment of 12-22 MPa in comparison onto first stage. This is possibly due to the moment that is applied via the implant being aggregated amongst the cortical and cancellous bone, thereby step downing the stress in the contact of the implant thread. Consequently, the stress peak occurs 1 mm away from the implant. It ranges from 23-30 MPa stress profiles, occurs at the implant top, which is double as in the preceding stage.

Table 2: Results of the simulations performed at different depths of dental implant torque varying with respect to time

S/N	MATERIAL	DEPTH (mm)	STRESS		STRAIN	DEFORMATION (mm)
			Cortical	in MPa Cancellous		
1	Ti Alloy	0.5	11.709	0.9560	0.0506	0.0068
2		1	17.005	4.2639	0.00016	0.00012
3		2	25.52	3.4318	0.0155	0.00543
4		3-7	34.992	1.049	0.0077	0.00019
5		8	9.8149	3.9835	0.00540	0.00195
6		9	17.475	5.3693	0.00207	0.01130
7		10	23.776	5.2319	0.00247	0.0310
8		11	32.951	4.8446	0.0166	0.0105
9	CFR-PEEK	0.5	8.5862	0.8421	0.0021	0.00166
10		1	9.3958	2.2968	0.00535	0.00177
11		2	12.817	3.0908	0.00252	0.00118
12		3-7	21.583	1.6572	0.00118	0.00028
13		8	12.979	4.3138	0.00434	0.00241
14		9	17.568	4.6577	0.05638	0.0113
15		10	23.766	5.0936	0.03016	0.07575
16		11	32.951	4.8446	0.0166	0.01057

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This simulation describes stress profiles during different stages of dental implant insertion using material Titanium and CFR-PEEK. The results represents that as the depth of insertion of dental implant increases the value of applied torque also increases varying with respect to time evaluated in Table 2. When the implant encounter fluid (blood vessels) the strain dissipates in the three bodies two bones and blood interface.

To accurately simulate this process, frictional contact is used. For analysing the interaction that occurs between contacting bodies, the ANSYS Software offers a variety of settings, namely frictional, free of friction, rough, bonded, no separation, and additional. In cemented contact, the bodies are perfectly glued together, whereas sliding motion is allowed in frictional contact. For interaction between the cement layer and abutment, the abutment and fixture, and the cancellous bone and cortical bone, bonded contact is used.

The von Mises stresses are plotted at selected salient axes parallel the cancellous and cortical bones for every stage of implant insertion. The stress level increases with an increase in torque for all insertion depths. During the starting stage, the implant only comes in liaison with the cortical bone, resulting in adequately lessen stress in the cancellous bone. The stress magnitude decreases significantly as far as the implant is located. The stress reduction within the cancellous bone is expected due to the initial layer of interstitial blood and fragments of, which comes into proximity to the cortical bone. The top bottom segment of cancellous bone received greater stress levels. Maximum stress on the cortical bone was close towards the implant neck, and it grew with intervals and implantation depth. Since the implant is in having linear interaction therewith the cancellous bone at the implant's base

without any blood-bone interface, have high stress.

The stress distribution in the top portion of the implant is not significantly affected by friction coefficients that fluctuate between 0.1 to 0.4 sec. The highest stress values are observed in the cortical bone at the top bone-implant interaction, rather than in the cancellous bone. Cortical bone having high Young's modulus can absorb more torque than the cancellous bone. The findings suggest that no discernible change exists in stress distribution among the titanium alloy and PEEK studied. The cortical bone has both the greatest maximal and lowest minimal primary stresses.

As different models are simulated, the level of strains ascends 0.0035 mm. Specifically, the induced strain is found to be the highest when it comes to the PEEK implant. The maximum deformation in all the models is mostly around 0.01 due to the varied applied torque. All models have strains 0.001 to 0.021mm. Figure 4 shows the deformation and strain caused due to applied torque to the implant-bone model. In every model that is analyzed, it is observed that the implant-bone interface consistently experienced the greatest amount of strain.

However, these findings contradict the clinical observations that dental implants are highly successful. One possible explanation is considering the principles of "Frost's mechanostat theory", which accommodate long skeletal bones well and may not be applicable to alveolar bone. The study's findings will help dentists to carry out a patient specific implant procedure in an enhanced quality controlled way.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The research proposes an effective 3- dimensional modelling method to investigate stress distribution due to time-dependent torque during the implantation process, considering the biomechanical implant-jawbone relationship as well as realistic shape, material qualities, loading, and support requirements for the corresponding implant and the jawbone.

The study evaluates load transfer and stress distribution in peri-implant bone. The research identifies that the choice of contact type between occlusal surfaces can result in inaccurate stress distribution, and friction coefficients have minimal effect.

Future research will explore the impact of designing different screw geometries and complex bone structures. In accordance with on initial findings, more advanced methods could be used to fully simulate the dynamic implantation process.

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